

accelerate cold tolerance breeding for high-elevation and high-latitude areas where only 1 rice crop/year is possible.

Bulk seeds of F₃ to F₅ RGA populations of photoperiod-sensitive materials and cold-tolerant crosses will be available for distribution early in 1980. Scientists may obtain a list of the materials by writing to the authors. It is hoped that plant breeders will take advantage of this IRRI service.

Two new rice varieties released in Bihar, India

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Two new rice varieties, Rajendra Dhan 201 and Rajendra Dhan 202, were recently named by Rajendra Agricultural University and released for cultivation in Bihar.

Rajendra Dhan 201 (from the cross IR8/Tadukan) has intermediate growth duration (135 days) and is suitable for irrigated transplanted areas. It has yielded 5 t/ha. It has medium-slender grain and disease resistance. Before its release, Rajendra Dhan 201 was tested for 6 years in experimental plots, and 3 years in minikits in farmers' fields.

Rajendra Dhan 202 (from the cross IR8/W1251) was previously known by its line number, RP9-4. It is suitable for gall midge-endemic areas of Chhotanagpur. It was tested through the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program and in minikits in farmers' fields. The variety matures in 125 days and has long, bold grains. Its yields average 4.4 t/ha. When gall midge attack is severe, Rajendra Dhan 202 yields 70 to 80% higher than Jaya or IR8.

Isolation of single cells from rice

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A new method to isolate single cells from rice leaves was developed using the

varieties Taichung 65 and Tainan 5. The method consists of mechanically pregrinding the leaf blades and macerating the leaf fragments in pectinase. The isolated single cells, as seen through a phase contrast microscope, were columnar and lobed. Their number varied with the age of the leaves used and the time of maceration. About 10⁵ to 10⁶ cells/g of fresh leaves were isolated in 3 hours' maceration. Leaf tissues from the same variety yielded more single cells when used at 34 days old than at 101 days. The number of single cells isolated did not differ significantly between the two varieties.

Screening of rice cultivars against bird damage

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Two thousand rice cultivars, maintained at the germplasm center, Baronda, were field screened against bird damage during 1978 kharif. Each cultivar was sown in 3 rows spaced 20 cm apart.

Scoring was based on the percentage of damaged grains. No cultivar escaped bird damage; 13 had as much as 10% damage and 1,987 had more than 60%. Cultivars damaged least were Ajan, Ajwaine, Barhi, Danwar, Dawar, Koliar, Lakhokuwar, Manjhaligurmatia, Nunji, Parhi, Ratna, Surjajota, and Surmatia. Cultivars with brown- to black-husked grain showed less bird damage. ■

SR26BM, an EMS-induced mutant variety that is insensitive to photoperiod

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The variety SR26B is well adapted to saline soils in the irrigated tract of Karnataka, India. But its photoperiod sensitivity limits its cultivation to the wet season.

Hybridization of SR26B with Waner 1 gave fine-grained lines with early maturity, but the yield potential and the puffing quality of the grain were lost. Therefore, a study to obtain an isogenic mutant of SR26B with

photoperiod insensitivity was initiated in 1972 at the Regional Research Station, Mandya, in collaboration with the Plant., Breeding Department, Agricultural College, Bangalore.

After presoaking in tap water for 10 hours, 200 g of SR26B seed was soaked in 1% EMS solution without buffer for 14 hours. The EMS had been prepared in double distilled water; the volume of solution used was three times that of the seed. The seeds in the solution were constantly shaken and maintained at a room temperature of about 21 °C. Both treated and control seeds were then washed with tap water 20 times. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill in January 1973 at Bangalore to grow during the dry season. In May, a plant with normal panicle exertion and flowering that resembled the original SR26B in spikelet and other plant characters was noticed in the treated plot. No other plant, treated or control, flowered at that time. But photoperiod-insensitive varieties planted at about the same time in a performance test flowered. Thus, the plant under consideration could only be a mutant of SR26B. It was seeded at Mandya in the 1973 wet season. Because all the plants looked alike they were bulk harvested and the mutant was designated SR26BM. It bred true when raised at Mandya in the 1974 dry season.

Since the variant appeared in the M₁ and bred true in subsequent generations, it could only be a homozygous recessive mutant. Reports of such mutants appearing in *Lycopersicon* in the M₁ were published in 1968. In such cases, the M₁ mutant seedlings arise from simultaneous mutation of the locus concerned in both homozygous chromosomes because the mutagen is highly

Grain yield performance of SR26BM in Salt Tolerant Variety Trials in Karnataka, India, 1977.

Season	Location	Yield (t/ha)	
		SR26BM	SR26B
Dry	Hiriyur	6.1	—
Wet	Hiriyur	2.8	3.5
Wet	Mandya	2.1	2.1
Wet	Gangavathi	5.7	5.3

effective.

SR26BM was evaluated for yield in the regular Salt Tolerant Variety Trial (see table). The yield potential and puffing quality of the grain seemed unaffected. The plant type of SR26BM—tall and weak—needs improvement, but the variety can be cultivated in the dry season in salt-affected soils. ■

BW100, a promising new variety in Sri Lanka

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BW100, a sister line of BW78, was selected in 1976 from the cross H50I//Podiwee A-8/H5. Since 1976 it has consistently yielded higher than BW78. Its gall midge resistance was shown in 1977 and 1978 yala, when it outyielded several varieties, including BG11-11.

In the 1978 Yala National Coordinated Rice Varietal Trials tested at 14 locations, BW100 gave the highest mean yield—11.4 t/ha under various soil and climatic conditions. In the 1977-78 Maha Extension Field Trials, it outyielded BW78 in six of seven districts.

The intermediate-statured BW100 matures in 4–4.5 months; responds well to nitrogen; has lodging resistance, weed competitive ability, superior grain quality, and resistance to storage pests; and performs well under adverse soil and climatic conditions. ■

Sita: a variety for irrigated wetlands of Bihar, India

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In 1975, the variety Sita (from the cross IR12-178-2-3/IR8) was released in Bihar for the intensively cropped irrigated areas.

Sita's relatively short growth duration (130-135 days, seed to seed) enables farmers to harvest by early November, then plant a winter crop such as wheat.

Yields average 4 to 6 t/ha. Farmers prefer Sita to Jaya because it responds better to low levels of fertilizer (40–50 kg N/ha); it has long, slender grain; it is moderately resistant to tungro, blast, and bacterial blight; and its flowering is synchronous. Bihar farmers have adopted Sita widely and the variety is moving into Uttar Pradesh. ■

Optimal use of space and plant containers in RGA

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Rapid generation advance (RGA) makes it possible to have 3 generations/year of breeding materials by reducing the growth duration, shortening the day length, and using high temperature. Spacing must also be close to plant thousands of progeny lines in a greenhouse of limited size. Use of large wooden boxes or individual plots has advantages and disadvantages. More plants can be accommodated in wooden boxes, but those boxes remain occupied until the last plant is harvested. Small pots take more space – but half of that space may be available 3 months after sowing. If plants are stressed at an early stage, elimination of susceptible lines provides additional space within a month after sowing.

An experiment was conducted at IRRI to study plant responses and advantages of different containers. Pregerminated F₂ seeds of the cross IR24389 (Sein Ta Lay (X69-2-27)/IR36//BKN6986-147-2), designated as RGA 079 were planted in wooden boxes, square pots, and round pots. The measurements of the wooden boxes were 1.27 × 1.27 × 0.1 m; each accommodated 1,600 plants at a spacing of 3 × 3 cm. In an equivalent area, 440 square pots (5.5 × 5.5 × 5.0 cm) can be accommodated but only 272 round pots (6.7 cm diam, 5 cm ht). We used Maahas soil mixed with ammonium sulfate, solophos, and muriate of potash at the rate of 4-2-2 g/4 kg of soil. The plants were grown in the greenhouse under natural day length until the 5th-leaf stage; then they were subjected

to a short-day treatment of 10 hours light and 14 hours darkness. Additional nitrogen fertilizer was applied at the rate of 20 g ammonium sulfate/box at 15-day intervals.

The wooden box accommodated twice as many plants per unit of space as the pots did. The population reached 50% flowering at about the same time regardless of container. That means that half of a population planted in pots can be harvested after 90 days. The vacated space can be used to start another set of cross progeny. When wooden boxes are used, the space vacated is wasted and the box cannot be used to full efficiency until the last plant is harvested.

The number of plants processed per year is essentially the same regardless of whether wooden boxes or square pots are used. Wooden boxes may have an advantage for early generation materials that are not screened or selected and that require small amounts of seeds per plant.

The closer spacing of the large wooden box resulted in more dead plants at harvest. Closer spacing means more competition - not only for nutrients, even more so for light. In the wooden box, 74% of the plants survived; in the square pots 99% did; and in the round pots, 100%.

For screening, the individual plant containers are definitely better than the large wood boxes. Susceptible plants can be eliminated after testing; the remaining few plants can grow to maturity in a much smaller space.

The square pot is ideal for RGA screening, which is usually done at the F₄ or F₅ generation. In RGA, more seeds are needed for distribution to plant breeders because panicles are larger and scientists can easily discard dead or susceptible plants. ■

Rice breeding progress at Bombuwela, Sri Lanka

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The variety H4 was released in 1959 and, like IR8 in Southeast Asia, it initiated the so-called green revolution in Sri Lanka. It